

1 **Activation of POLL by HPV16 E7.**

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6 E7 molecular functions, binding partners and network interactants remain incompletely defined. We
7 studied E7 molecular function through measurement of total transcription by RNA-sequencing in HPV-
8 C33A cells following ectopic expression of HPV16 E7. We demonstrate here activation of *Poll* by HPV16
9 HPV E7.

10 Citations

11 1. McLaughlin-Drubin, M.E. and Münger, K., 2009. The human papillomavirus E7 oncoprotein.
12 *Virology*, 384(2), pp.335-344.

13 2. García-Díaz, M., Domínguez, O., López-Fernández, L.A., de Lera, L.T., Saníger, M.L., Ruiz, J.F.,
14 Párraga, M., García-Ortiz, M.J., Kirchhoff, T., Del Mazo, J. and Bernad, A., 2000. DNA polymerase lambda
15 (Pol λ), a novel eukaryotic DNA polymerase with a potential role in meiosis. *Journal of molecular biology*,
16 301(4), pp.851-867.

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